

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

ASSESSMENT OF THE CAUSATIVE FACTORS CAUSING COMPLICATIONS AFTER ILLEOSTOMY CLOSURE

Dr. Nadia Riaz¹, Dr. Muhammad Danish Shabbir², Dr. Nadeem Walayat³¹ Nishtar Medical College Multan, ² Frontier Medical and Dental College, Abbottabad, ³ Quaid e Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur.

Article Received: June 2020

Accepted: July 2020

Published: August 2020

Abstract:**Objectives:** To evaluate the causes of complications after ileostomy reversal.**Study design:** An observational study.**Place and duration:** In the Surgical department of Nishtar Hospital Multan for one -year duration from April 2019 to April 2020.**Methodology:** The study included 46 consecutive patients who underwent ileostomy reversal within one year. We excluded patients under 12 years of age, patients who were confined within 6 weeks, and patients with additional, unrelated surgical intervention. All patients were followed up at weekly intervals for one month. The main endpoint was the occurrence of surgical complications within 30 days of reversal.**Results:** A series of 46 post-ileostomy closures were analyzed to evaluate factors contributing to morbidity and mortality. There were no deaths, but the complication rate was 10.9% (5 patients), with the most common complications being wound infection (4.35%) and anastomotic leak (4.35%) and paralytic ileus (2.17%). Primary closure of the stoma site, the technique of anastomotic closure, type of stoma, and the surgeon's experience were significant contributing factors.**Conclusion:** We concluded that ileostomy closure has few complications but no mortality. The techniques of closure of the anastomotic site, type of stoma, surgeon's experience, and skin closure technique were predictors of complications.**Key words:** ileostomy closure, anastomotic leak, ileostomy stroma.**Corresponding author:**

Dr. Nadia Riaz,

Nishtar Medical College Multan.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Nadia Riaz et al, *Assessment Of The Causative Factors Causing Complications After Ileostomy Closure.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(08).

INTRODUCTION:

In general surgery, stoma formation is a common procedure for both elective and emergency surgery. In the late nineteenth century, colostomies were used to treat intestinal obstruction [1-2]. An intestinal stoma has been considered a drastic procedure due to its high number of complications. As surgical techniques have improved, the need for a stoma has increased [3-4]. An Ileostomy is a life-saving procedure that enables individuals to enjoy the full range of daily life activities. Ileostomies are necessary when the ileum is distant from the stoma or the large intestine is diseased or damaged. An ileostomy may be temporary or permanent, depending on the indication for surgery [5-6]. A temporary ileostomy is usually removed after a while. Although it lowers the operational risk of the first indication, after its closure it is associated with some morbidity and mortality [7-8]. Regarding the complications, the presented series show conflicting results. Thus, incidence rates range from 2.4% to 48.2% after temporary stoma closure [9-10]. The most common surgical complications after stoma closure are wound infections, anastomotic leak, paralytic ileus, small bowel obstruction, and bleeding. Various patient and technique risk factors influencing post-closure complications. These complications affect the health of the patient and increase the postoperative hospital stay, as well as increase the costs of hospitalization.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was performed in the Surgical department of Nishtar Hospital Multan for one -year duration from April 2019 to April 2020. All subsequent illeostomy closure patients after 8 weeks of illeostomy reversal were enrolled in the study. Patients under 12 years of age, patients undergoing confinement within 6 weeks, and additional, unrelated surgical intervention were excluded. Demographic data, indications for temporary illeostomy and operational details were recorded. Distal loopogram using Barium was performed in all patients prior to closure. Patients had routine mechanical debridement of the proximal and distal bowel with discontinuation of oral feeding the day before surgery and lavage with oral mannitol solution and lavage of distal loops with saline prior to surgery. All patients received parenteral antibiotics (ceftriaxone and metronidazole) during induction which was continued for 5 days. All patients consented to laparotomy when necessary. An

elliptical periosteal incision was made and the stoma was mobilized from the surrounding fascial and peritoneal adhesions. After refreshing the margins of the enterotomy, leaving the mesenteric side intact and closing the enterotomy transversely, using a single layer, hand-sewn, additional mucosa, using the intermittent technique with a delayed absorbable suture. The muscle gap was closed with prolene 0 interrupted sutures. All skin incisions were closed predominantly with 2/0 interrupted sutures and an aseptic dressing was applied. Complications have been reported during hospital stay and those reported during the monthly one-week follow-up after discharge. Wound infections, anastomotic leakage and paralytic ileus were considered surgical complications.

Several risk factors related to the operation have been noted. The result was the presence of complications from surgery within 30 days. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 18.0. A p value below 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

46 patients participated in the study. All patients underwent emergency surgery. The age range of these patients was 14-80 years, mean age 42.8 years, and SD 1.6. 28 patients (61%) are male and 18 patients (39%) are female. The most common indication for an illeostomy 15 was externalization of typhoid fever in ileal perforation (32.6%). This was followed by abdominal tuberculosis 11 (23.9%), penetrating abdominal trauma 7 (15.2%), intestinal gangrene 7 (15.2%), blunt abdominal trauma 2 (04.35), colonic obstruction 2 (04, 3%), post-laparotomy 1 (02.2%), ileal perforation post-abortion 1 (02.2%). The ileum was introduced as a loop in most patients, followed by a double-spike illeostomy, illeostomy, and terminal illeostomy with a distant mucous fistula. (Table 1) Median time interval between stoma construction and stoma closure was 14 weeks (range 7-35, mean 15 ± 6.8) Forty-two (42) closures were performed by an elliptical incision around an ileostomy, while four (4) required a laparotomy . All anastomoses were made using a single-layer technique with disruption, extracellularly, with the use of delayed absorbable suture material. The loops were inverted by transverse closure after reshaping the edges, while in the remaining cases the short segment of the intestine was removed and an end-to-end anastomosis was performed.

Table 1: Types of Ileostomy

Type of stoma	No. of patients
Loop ileostomy	29 (63.0%)
Double barrel ileostomy	14 (30.4%)
Ileocolostomy	02 (04.3%)
End ileostomy with distant mucus fistula	01 (02.2%)

The median duration of the operation was 60 minutes (range 45-120 minutes). The intraperitoneal drains were placed at the discretion of the operating surgeon. In 19 (41.3%), wave drains were used in wounds. 18 stoma closures (39.1%) were supervised

directly, and 28 stoma closures (60.9%) were performed by consultants. The mean stay after the operation was 6 days. (Median 5, range 4-15, SD $\pm$ 2.21 days) There was no operative mortality.

Table 2: Patient related risk factors for complications after ileostomy closure

Risk factors	With Compli- cations (n=5)	Without complications (n=41)	p-value
Age in years (median)	49(15-80)	38 (14-65)	0.12
Gender			
Male	03(40%)	31(75.6%)	0.128
Female	02(60%)	10(24.4%)	
Type of stoma			
Loop ileostomy	01(20%)	28(68.3%)	0.079
Double barrel ileostomy	02(40%)	10(24.4%)	
Ileocolostomy	01(20%)	02(4.9%)	
End colostomy	01(20%)	01(2.4%)	
Reason for ileostomy			
Typhoid perforation	01(20%)	15(36.6%)	0.421
Abdominal tuberculosis	01(20%)	10(24.4%)	
Penetrating abdominal trauma	00(0%)	07(17.1%)	
Bowel gangrene	02(40%)	05(12.2%)	
Blunt abdominal trauma	01(20%)	01(2.4%)	
Large bowel obstruction	00(0%)	02(4.8%)	
Post-laparotomy Ileal perforation	00(0%)	01(2.4%)	
Post-abortion ileal perforation	00(0%)	01(2.4%)	

Complications related to the operation occurred in five patients (10.9%). The most common complications were wound infection and anastomotic leak. Leaks occurred in 2 patients (4.35%), 1 of which required relaparotomy. The other had a low-output fistula that responded to conservative

treatment. Wound infection was found in 2 (4.35%) patients who were treated with simple drainage and oral antibiotics depending on culture and sensitivity. Paralytic Ileus occurred in 1 patient (2.17%) treated conservatively Table 2.

Table 3: Operation technique related risk factors for complications after illeostomy closure.

Risk factors	With complications n=5	Without complications n=41
Median Interval(weeks) from construction to closure	14 (10-21)	14 (7-35)
Type of anastomosis		
End to end closure	03	06
Enterotomy closure	02	35
Surgical approach		
Relaparotomy	02	02
Closure at illeostomy site	03	39
Surgeons experience		
Supervised trainee	03	15
Consultant.	02	26
Drains		
Used	03	15
Not used	02	26
Duration of surgery in min Median (range)	60(45-120)	60(45-90)

DISCUSSION:

Temporary stoma formation of the small intestine is a common surgical procedure, both elective and emergency, to protect the distal anastomosis or to avoid intraperitoneal anastomosis if the environment is hostile [9-10]. It is generally recommended that you close your temporary stoma within 9-12 weeks. However, some patients do not tolerate a temporary stoma due to a poor fit of the pouch, leading to premonition of the surrounding skin, dehydration, electrolyte imbalance and nutritional deficiencies, so you may opt for early closure. Closing the illeostomy may be associated with mortality and morbidity. The presented series showed conflicting results for morbidity and mortality rates. But the overall complication rate after an illeostomy closure ranges between 2.4% -48.2%. Various factors are responsible for complications after an illeostomy is closed. Such as skin closure techniques and anastomotic sites, surgeon's experience, type of stoma, and the intervals between primary surgery and closure. In our study, surgical complications requiring reoperation that could be treated conservatively were considered morbid. Wound infection is a common complication after stoma closure. It ranges from 1.3% -14.2% depending on

the skin closing technique. Various techniques have been used to close skin wounds [11]. The rate of infections associated with wound closure by secondary intent is low, but it causes a very unsightly scar and extends hospital stay. Primary shutdown is usually associated with a high infection rate. However, the use of broad-spectrum antibiotics together with primary containment gives good results in terms of the cosmetic infection rate and hospital stay. Delayed primary wound closure also has a low infection rate at the wound site. Lee JR et al; observed a low infection rate when the string technique was used instead of linear closure [12-13]. A catastrophic complication of intestinal anastomosis is an anastomotic leak, leading to peritonitis, which is associated with high morbidity and mortality. The percentage of complications with leakage of 5-8% at the anastomotic site has been documented. It was observed that the time interval from onset to closure had a significant impact on the complication rate ($p < 0.0001$). Anastomotic leakage was small in those who underwent closure after 90 days than in those who were less than 30 days old. Surgeon's experience is another factor influencing the complication rate of stoma reversal. Low anastomotic leakage takes place. Various techniques of anastomotic closure have been

used to control complications of anastomotic line. It has been observed that the closure of the loop has fewer complications at the suture line than in the case of split stomas. This is most likely because there is less need to dissect the mesentery in the closure of the loop than in split stomas. However, according to S.A Garcia-Botello et al [14-15]. There are no statistically significant differences in the incidence of occlusion techniques ($p = 0.892$). Paralytic ileus and small intestine obstruction are other complications seen after stoma inversion. The reported incidence varies in different series from 4% to 16.6%. Paralytic ileus is most likely caused by electrolyte imbalance and small intestine obstruction due to postoperative adhesions. They both usually respond well to conservative treatment, and surgery is rarely indicated.

CONCLUSION:

Ileostomy reversal is not free from complications. However, it was concluded that anastomotic closure techniques, stoma type, surgeon's experience, and skin closure technique were predictors of complications. Loop closure, enterotomy using the retrocecal technique gives better results than resection and end-to-end anastomosis. The risk of wound infection and dehiscence is low for delayed primary skin closure than for primary skin closure.

REFERENCES:

- Goh, Hui Lu, Lauren Hawkins, Sivesh K. Kamarajah, Sharad Karandikar, and Mark Goldstein. "Is water-soluble contrast enema examination for integrity of rectal anastomosis necessary prior to ileostomy reversal?." *JGH Open* (2019).
- Okuya, Koichi, Ichiro Takemasa, Tetsuhiro Tsuruma, Ai Noda, Kenichi Sasaki, Tomomi Ueki, Mitsuhiro Mukaiya et al. "Evaluation of negative-pressure wound therapy for surgical site infections after ileostomy closure in colorectal cancer patients: a prospective multicenter study." *Surgery Today* (2020): 1-7.
- Ng, Kheng-Seong, Simon Joseph Gonsalves, and Peter Michael Sagar. "Ileal-anal pouches: A review of its history, indications, and complications." *World journal of gastroenterology* 25, no. 31 (2019): 4320.
- Ahmad, Hira, Andrew B. Nordin, Devin R. Halleran, Brian Kenney, Preeti Jaggi, Alessandra Gasior, Laura Weaver, Alejandra Vilanova Sanchez, Richard J. Wood, and Marc A. Levitt. "Decreasing surgical site infections in pediatric stoma closures." *Journal of Pediatric Surgery* 55, no. 1 (2020): 90-95.
- Kee, Youn Kyung, HyOUNGNAE Kim, Jong Hyun Jhee, Seung Hyeok Han, Tae-Hyun Yoo, Shin-Wook Kang, and Jung Tak Park. "Incidence of and risk factors for delayed acute kidney injury in patients undergoing colorectal surgery." *The American Journal of Surgery* 218, no. 5 (2019): 907-912.
- Cho, Jung Rae, Byung jun Yoon, and Heung-Kwon Oh. "939–Effect of Probiotics on Bowel Function Restoration After Ileostomy Reversal in Patients with Rectal Cancer: A Double-Blind Randomized Controlled Trial." *Gastroenterology* 156, no. 6 (2019): S-1421.
- Sun, Xiyu, Huiqiao Han, Huizhong Qiu, Bin Wu, Guole Lin, Beizhan Niu, Jiaolin Zhou et al. "Comparison of safety of loop ileostomy and loop transverse colostomy for low-lying rectal cancer patients undergoing anterior resection: A retrospective, single institution, propensity score-matched study." *Asia-Pacific Journal of Clinical Oncology* (2020).
- Bosaily, Ahmad, John Edminister, Samarchitha Magal, Mohammad Jamil, Amy Lynn, and Glenn Hall. "Extensive Circumferential Heterotopic Ossification Discovered at the Base of a Loop Ileostomy." *Case Reports in Surgery* 2019 (2019).
- Bonin, Elodie, Valérie Bridoux, Rachid Chati, Sabrina Kermiche, Julien Coget, Jean Jacques Tuech, and Horace Roman. "Diverting stoma-related complications following colorectal endometriosis surgery: a 163-patient cohort." *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology* 232 (2019): 46-53.
- Reddy, Vikram B., and Walter E. Longo. "Ileostomy." In *Shackelford's Surgery of the Alimentary Tract, 2 Volume Set*, pp. 991-1004. Content Repository Only!, 2019.
- Grass, Fabian, James Ansell, Molly Petersen, Kellie L. Mathis, and Amy L. Lightner. "Risk factors for 90-day readmission and return to the operating room following abdominal operations for Crohn's disease." *Surgery* 166, no. 6 (2019): 1068-1075.
- Leão, Pedro, Catarina Santos, André Goulart, Ana Célia Caetano, Maria Sousa, Gerrit Hogemann, Amjad Parvaiz, and Nuno Figueiredo. "TaTME: analysis of the evacuatory outcomes and EUS anal sphincter." *Minimally Invasive Therapy & Allied Technologies* 28, no. 6 (2019): 332-337.
- Horisberger, Karoline, Carmen Portenkirchner, Andreas Rickenbacher, Luc Biedermann, Christoph Gubler, and Matthias Turina.

- "Complete Recovery of Immune Checkpoint Inhibitor-induced Colitis by Diverting Loop Ileostomy." *Journal of Immunotherapy* 43, no. 4 (2020): 145-148.
14. Sharp, Stephen P., Ashar Ata, A. David Chismark, Jonathan J. Canete, Brian T. Valerian, Steven D. Wexner, and Edward C. Lee. "Racial disparities after stoma construction in colorectal surgery." *Colorectal Disease* 22, no. 6 (2020): 713-722.
 15. Yamamoto, Takayuki, Michele Carvello, Amy Lee Lightner, Antonino Spinelli, and Paulo Gustavo Kotze. "Up-to-date surgery for ulcerative colitis in the era of biologics." *Expert Opinion on Biological Therapy* 20, no. 4 (2020): 391-398.